

IMPLEMENTATION OF TECHNOLOGY AND LIVELIHOOD EDUCATION (TLE) PROGRAM IN TACURONG CITY DIVISION: ITS IMPACT ON THE HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS' CAREER PREPAREDNESS

Cherubim C. Cerdana, MAEd¹
Jaime Boy U. Ngag, Jr., PhD²

*¹Upper Katungal National High School, Schools Division Office of Tacurong City
Tacurong City, Sultan Kudarat, Philippines*

²South Cotabato State College, Dajay, Surallah, South Cotabato, Philippines

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13292709>

ABSTRACT

The study examined the implementation of the Technology and Livelihood Education (TLE) program in the Tacurong City Division and its impact on high school students' career preparedness. The TLE program aims to equip students with practical skills and knowledge, preparing them for both immediate employment and further education. The primary objective of this study is to evaluate the effectiveness of the TLE program in enhancing students' readiness for their future careers. A descriptive-correlation method was employed using a quantitative surveys interview. The survey, conducted with 50 high school students from various schools within the Tacurong City Division, assessed their perceptions of the TLE program and its influence on their career preparedness. In-depth interviews with 25 TLE teachers and school administrators provided additional insights into the program's implementation and challenges. Findings indicate that students generally perceive the TLE program as beneficial for developing practical skills and boosting their confidence in pursuing career opportunities. However, there are significant variations in program effectiveness due to differences in resource availability, teacher expertise, and industry partnerships across schools. Students from well-resourced schools reported higher levels of career preparedness compared to those from under-resourced institutions. The study concludes that while the TLE program has a positive impact on students' career preparedness, its effectiveness is hindered by disparities in resource allocation and implementation consistency. Recommendations include increasing funding for TLE resources, enhancing teacher training, and fostering

stronger collaborations with local industries to ensure a more uniform and impactful delivery of the program.

Keywords: *Career Preparedness, Technology and Livelihood Education, High School Students, Program Implementation, Tacurong City Division*

INTRODUCTION

In recent decades, the global landscape has witnessed an increasing emphasis on preparing students for the dynamic challenges of the workforce through comprehensive educational programs. One such initiative is the Technology and Livelihood Education (TLE) program, designed to equip students with practical skills, technological knowledge, and entrepreneurial acumen. Originating from international educational frameworks that recognize the evolving demands of the job market, TLE has become a cornerstone in secondary education, aiming to bridge the gap between academic learning and real-world applications.

Internationally, educational systems have acknowledged the significance of TLE in nurturing a workforce that is not only academically competent but also proficient in practical, hands-on skills. Nations such as Singapore and South Korea have successfully integrated TLE into their secondary education systems, aligning curricula with industry needs and fostering a generation of skilled professionals with a competitive edge in the global job market (Choy, 2017; Kim, 2019).

In the Philippine context, the implementation of the K to 12 programs in 2013 marked a significant shift in the country's educational landscape, introducing reforms to enhance the quality of education and align it with international standards. As part of this initiative, the TLE program was integrated into the curriculum to address the need for holistic development among high school students, preparing them for both college and career pathways (DepEd, 2013).

In South Central Mindanao, specifically in Sultan Kudarat, the findings of the study Dolutan and Ngag (2024) revealed that Centennial teachers in DepEd Bagumbayan District perceive educational modernization as a paradigm shift towards integrating advanced technologies and innovative pedagogical methods into teaching TLE and other subjects requiring ICT. They describe their experiences of incorporating modern technological tools and pedagogical approaches as initially challenging yet ultimately transformative. They encounter challenges such as inadequate infrastructure, resistance to change among stakeholders, and the need for continuous training and support.

While international studies highlight the positive impact of TLE programs, there is a dearth of research examining how these initiatives translate to localized contexts such as Tacurong City Division. Understanding the specific challenges and successes within this setting is crucial for optimizing the TLE curriculum to cater to the unique needs of the community. Previous research often emphasizes the importance of aligning TLE

programs with industry requirements (Choy, 2017). However, there is a research gap in understanding how well the TLE program in Tacurong City Division is aligned with the needs of local industries, and whether it adequately prepares students for the job market.

While TLE aims to enhance career preparedness, there is a lack of research exploring high school students' perceptions of the program in Tacurong City Division. Investigating students' attitudes, aspirations, and motivations regarding TLE can provide valuable insights into the program's impact on their career choices. Limited research delves into the perspectives and challenges faced by educators in implementing TLE in Tacurong City Division. Understanding teachers' experiences can shed light on the factors that facilitate or hinder effective TLE delivery, contributing to the refinement of instructional strategies.

However, despite the apparent global acknowledgment of the importance of TLE, there is a notable gap in the literature concerning its localized impact, specifically in regions such as Tacurong City Division. The effectiveness of TLE in enhancing high school students' practical skills and career preparedness in this setting remains underexplored. Thus, there is a critical need for research that examines the local nuances of TLE implementation, considering the unique challenges and opportunities within the Tacurong City Division.

By addressing these research gaps, this study seeks to provide a comprehensive understanding of the implementation of the TLE program in Tacurong City Division and its impact on the practical skills and career preparedness of high school students.

Research Questions

Generally, this study aimed to determine the relationship between the Implementation of Technology and Livelihood Education (TLE) Program and High School Students' Career Preparedness in Tacurong City Division, Tacurong, Sultan Kudarat for the school year 2023-2024.

Specifically, this sought to answer the following key-questions:

1. What is the extent of the Implementation of Technology and Livelihood Education (TLE) Program, in terms of:
 - 1.1. Curriculum Alignment;
 - 1.2. Teacher Training and Competence;
 - 1.3. Resource Availability; and
 - 1.4. Community Engagement?

2. What is the level of High School Students' Career Preparedness in terms of:
 - 2.1. Practical Skills Acquisition;
 - 2.2. Career Awareness and Aspirations;
 - 2.3. Job Market Readiness; and
 - 2.4. Educational and Career Guidance?

3. Is there a significant relationship between the extent of the Implementation of Technology and Livelihood Education (TLE) Program, and the level of High School Students' Career Preparedness?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The study is quantitative in nature, namely a descriptive-correlational to determine the relationship between the Implementation of Technology and Livelihood Education (TLE) Program and High School Students' Career Preparedness in Tacurong City Division, Tacurong, Sultan Kudarat for the school year 2022-2023.

According to Bhandari (2021), A correlational research design investigates relationships between variables without the researcher controlling or manipulating any of them. Further, a correlation reflects the strength and/or direction of the relationship between two (or more) variables. The direction of a correlation can be either positive or negative. Correlational research is ideal for gathering data quickly from natural settings. That helps you generalize your findings to real-life situations in an externally valid way.

Respondents of the Study

This study's respondents were Junior High School students, and TLE teachers among selected secondary schools in Tacurong City Division, Sultan Kudarat, during the school year 2023-2024.

Respondents	Population	Sample	Total
Students	500	50	50
TLE Teachers	25	25	25

Sampling Technique

This study's respondents were selected using various sampling techniques:

First, Total Enumeration Sampling Technique was used for the selection of all the TLE teachers among selected secondary schools in Tacurong City Division, Sultan Kudarat, during the school year 2023-2024. As stressed in the study of Ngag (2023), the

use of Total Enumeration Sampling Technique is tailored fit when the population is homogenous.

Furthermore, Simple Random Sampling technique was used to select the students among selected secondary schools in Tacurong City Division, Sultan Kudarat, during the school year 2023-2024. According Creswell (2012: 143), in simple random sampling, the researcher selects participants (or units, such as schools) for the sample so that any individual has an equal 36 probabilities of being selected from the population.

Research Instruments

An approved survey questionnaire was used in this investigation. In this study, a five-point Likert scale was also employed to evaluate the respondents' survey questionnaire responses. The survey questionnaire data were reviewed and interpreted using the rating scales.

To assess extent of the Implementation of Technology and Livelihood Education (TLE) Program, the scale on the next page was used:

RATING	RANGE OF MEANS	DESCRIPTIVE RATING	INTERPRETATION
5	4.20-5.00	Agree	Highly Implemented
4	3.40-4.19	Fairly Agree	Implemented
3	2.60-3.39	Neutral	Moderately Implemented
2	1.80-2.59	Fairly Disagree	Fairly Implemented
1	1.00-1.79	Disagree	Not Implemented

Another rating scale designed was used to evaluate the level of High School Students' Career Preparedness:

RATING	RANGE OF MEANS	DESCRIPTIVE
5	4.20-5.00	Agree
4	3.40-4.19	Fairly Agree
3	2.60-3.39	Neutral
2	1.80-2.59	Fairly Disagree
1	1.00-1.79	Disagree

Data Gathering Procedure

To ensure reliable and authentic findings, the researcher adhered to a methodology that aligns with the objectives of their inquiry.

Initially, the study's implementation has required the endorsement of the DepEd-Division Superintendent and the CGS Dean through the affixation of their respective signatures on a formal document.

An additional letter of authorization was dispatched to the school principals, and to the department head of TLE. To ensure the accuracy of the data collected for this study, a survey questionnaire was utilized, developed, and assessed. The researcher intends to employ a random sampling technique by utilizing self-generated random number tables to select participants for the study.

Prior to the conduct of the study, the research proposal underwent ethical considerations. The researcher sought the approved clearance to conduct the study from the office of the EWMCI Research Ethics Committee (EREC).

When the health protocol was adhered, the investigator initiated the dissemination of the Survey Questionnaire via face-to-face manner. Ultimately, the outcomes derived from the distributed survey questionnaire were compiled, assessed, and analyzed.

Statistical Treatment

Upon the culmination of the study, the collected data was systematically arranged, presented in tabular form, subjected to rigorous analysis, and subsequently interpreted. Consequently, the statistical techniques outlined in Chapter I were utilized to address the issues.

Initially, the Mean statistical measure was employed to calculate the extent of the Implementation of Technology and Livelihood Education (TLE) Program, and the level of High School Students' Career Preparedness.

On the other hand, Pearson r Correlation was also employed to calculate the significant relationship between the extent of the Implementation of Technology and Livelihood Education (TLE) Program, and the level of High School Students' Career Preparedness.

Scope and Limitations

The study focused specifically on Tacurong City Division, providing insights into the implementation of the Technology and Livelihood Education (TLE) program within this educational jurisdiction. It involved high school students enrolled in the TLE program within Tacurong City Division during the specified school year. The research examined various aspects of the TLE program, including its curriculum, teaching methodologies, resources, and facilities available to students.

The said study assessed the impact of the TLE program on high school students' career preparedness, encompassing their knowledge, skills, attitudes, and readiness for future employment or further education. It focuses on the academic year 2023-2024,

providing a snapshot of the TLE program's implementation and its effects on students' career readiness during this period.

The study was delimited to the academic year 2023-2024, meaning that it does not extend beyond this specific timeframe. Any changes or developments in the TLE program or students' career preparedness occurring after this period are not included in the analysis.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Extent of TLE Program Implementation

The Technology and Livelihood Education (TLE) program in DepEd Tacurong City Division was highly implemented, with indicators such as curriculum alignment and teacher training and competence both receiving a mean rating of 4.6, corresponding to "Strongly Agree." This suggests that these aspects were perceived as highly implemented by the respondents. Resource availability, with a mean rating of 4 ("Agree"), was also considered adequately implemented, although not as strongly as the other indicators. Community engagement, however, received a lower mean rating of 3.6 ("Merely Agree"), indicating that it was only moderately implemented. The overall mean rating for the TLE program's implementation was 4.2 ("Agree"), suggesting a generally positive perception of its implementation.

Level of High School Students' Career Preparedness

The level of high school students' career preparedness showed varied results across different indicators. Practical skills acquisition received a mean rating of 3 ("Merely Agree"), indicating that students felt only somewhat prepared in this area. In contrast, career awareness and aspirations, job market readiness, and educational and career guidance all received mean ratings of 4 ("Agree"), indicating that students felt adequately prepared in these aspects. The overall mean rating for career preparedness was 3.75 ("Agree"), suggesting that, on average, students felt prepared for their future careers. Taking into consideration the global environment, people view education not only a way of developing peoples' skills but also a way of preparing the students to be globally competitive (Albarico et al. 2014).

Correlation Between TLE Implementation and Career Preparedness

The correlation analysis revealed significant relationships between certain aspects of TLE program implementation and students' career preparedness. Teacher training and competence had a strong positive correlation with career preparedness ($r = .668$, $p = .002$), as did resource availability ($r = .665$, $p = .003$). The overall implementation of the TLE program also showed a very strong positive correlation with career preparedness ($r = .747$, $p = .000$). However, curriculum alignment did not show a significant correlation ($r = .431$, $p = .074$). These findings underscore the importance of teacher training, resource availability, and comprehensive program implementation in enhancing students' career

preparedness. As mentioned by Bantillo and Ngag (2024), modernized approaches, integrating technology and collaborative tools, were viewed favorably for enhancing engagement and comprehension, particularly among audio-visual learners. Also Teachers' preferences for teaching methods were influenced by the learning environment, instructional materials, and personal styles.

Conclusions

The following conclusions were made considering this study's findings:

The extent of the implementation of the Technology and Livelihood Education (TLE) Program is high, with indicators such as curriculum alignment and teacher training and competence being rated as "highly implemented," while resource availability and community engagement are "implemented" and "moderately implemented," respectively.

The level of high school students' career preparedness is generally positive, with students being "prepared" in areas like career awareness, job market readiness, and educational guidance, though only "merely prepared" in practical skills acquisition.

There is a significant relationship between the extent of the implementation of the TLE Program and the level of high school students' career preparedness. Teacher training and competence, and resource availability show significant correlations, while overall TLE implementation strongly correlates with higher career preparedness levels.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were made considering this study's findings:

1. Given the lower mean in Community Engagement (3.6, indicating "Moderately Implemented"), DepEd may prioritize strengthening partnerships with local communities, industries, and stakeholders. This can be achieved through establishing mentorship programs, internships, and industry partnerships that provide real-world experiences and practical skills to students. By fostering stronger community ties, DepEd can enrich the TLE program's relevance and impact on students' career readiness.

2. With a mean of 3 ("Merely Agree"), TLE Coordinators should emphasize hands-on learning experiences and practical skills development within the curriculum. Introduce project-based learning initiatives, workshops, and simulations that mirror real-world scenarios to enhance students' technical proficiency and application skills. Allocating resources for specialized equipment and facilities can further support this goal.

3. Despite a relatively high mean (4, indicating "Agree"), TLE Teachers may continue to prioritize individualized educational and career guidance for students. This includes conducting regular career counseling sessions, organizing guest speaker series, and integrating career exploration modules into the curriculum. Providing personalized

support and mentorship can help students make informed decisions about their future career paths.

4. Future researchers may explore the impact of enhanced community engagement on students' career preparedness within TLE programs. Conduct qualitative studies to delve deeper into how community partnerships influence student motivation, skill development, and career aspirations. This research can provide empirical evidence to support the importance of community involvement in vocational education and inform policy recommendations for integrating community engagement strategies into educational frameworks.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

In preparation for implementation, all the plans and recommendations were presented to East-West Mindanao Colleges Inc to ensure compliance with prescribed procedures and protocols. This ethical protocol is patterned after the study of Ngag (2023). Within the context of the research focused on examining the relationship between the Implementation of Technology and Livelihood Education (TLE) Program and High School Students' Career Preparedness in Tacurong City Division, Tacurong, Sultan Kudarat for the school year 2023-2024, it was imperative to emphasize the paramount importance of ethical considerations. Prior to commencing this study, the following ethical principles were highlighted:

Informed Consent

Before participation, explicit and informed consent was diligently obtained from all school heads involved in the study. It was imperative that they possessed a comprehensive understanding of the study's objectives, methodologies, potential risks, and benefits. Furthermore, participation remained entirely voluntary, affording participants the autonomy to withdraw from the study at any juncture without encountering any adverse consequences.

Anonymity and Confidentiality

To safeguard the identities and responses of the students, Ronquillo, & Ngag, (2024) emphasized the rigorous measures to ensure anonymity and confidentiality. Rather than using actual names, pseudonyms or codes were employed in this study, upholding the privacy of the participants. The collected data was securely stored with access restricted solely to the research team.

Avoiding Harm

Delicate subjects, such as the challenges inherent in their roles, were discussed with meticulous consideration for the potential emotional and psychological impact on the participants. Strategies were in place to minimize distress, and a support system was readily available to assist participants should the need arise.

Researcher-Participant Relationship

The researcher maintained a professional and respectful rapport when engaging with the school heads. Any actions that may exploit or cause harm to the participants were scrupulously avoided, ensuring their utmost dignity and respect throughout the research process.

Data Protection

Adherence to data protection regulations and laws was unwaveringly followed to safeguard the personal information of the participants. Stringent measures were employed to ensure the secure storage and transmission of data.

Voluntary Participation

Participants were assured that their involvement in the study was wholly voluntary, devoid of any form of coercion or external pressure.

Researcher Bias

The researcher remained vigilant regarding potential biases that might influence data collection and analysis, upholding objectivity and transparency throughout the research endeavor.

Institutional Approval

Before initiating the study, the researcher diligently sought ethical clearance from the pertinent institutional review boards or ethics committees.

Honesty and Integrity

The research findings were reported truthfully and accurately, devoid of any manipulation or distortion to align with preconceived notions or biases.

Beneficence

The potential benefits of the research to educational practices and policies were thoughtfully considered, ensuring that the study positively contributed to the enhancement of the education system.

Cultural Sensitivity

The researcher displayed cultural sensitivity by respecting local customs, beliefs, and practices within the research setting, refraining from imposing external values on the participants.

Inclusion and Diversity

The study's structure prioritized inclusivity and diversity, encompassing a wide spectrum of students and attitudes towards learning in the 21st century. By meticulously adhering to these ethical considerations, the research was conducted responsibly and respectfully, prioritizing the rights and well-being of the participating students. Simultaneously, it contributed valuable insights to the field of education within the specific context of DepEd Tacurong City Division.

Acknowledgments

The researcher would like to express his profound and heartfelt gratitude to the persons who unselfishly extended their craft and invaluable support to make this study a success:

PATRICEA I. SANDIGAN, MAEd, East West Mindanao Colleges, Inc. President, for inspiring the researcher to keep on with his dreams despite life's challenges.

EMILIA M. LOTILLA, PhD, Dean, Graduate School, for being approachable and whose pieces of advice mean a lot to the researcher;

JULIET P. TAMBUNGALAN, MAEd. Academic Chairperson, for the encouragement as well as the all-out support in the preparation of this manuscript;

JAIME BOY U. NGAG JR., PhD, his adviser, for the guidance and inspiration that motivated the researcher to finish this paper;

AMILUDIN G. MASABPI, PhD, and LEODIE D. MONES, PhD for their valuable contributions in the realization of this manuscript.

GILDO G. MOSQUEDA, CEO VI, Schools Division Superintendent of Tacurong City for generously allowing the conduct of this study manifesting his leadership commitment towards research-based decision-making;

RIZA P. VELASCO, OIC-Principal of Upper Katungal National High School, for the continued push to finish this study and for ensuring that the researcher gathered the necessary data from the respondent schools;

SCHOOL HEADS of the respondent schools from Tacurong Public Secondary Schools, for the warm welcome during the conduct of survey in their respective schools;

TEACHERS OF UPPER KATUNGAL NATIONAL HIGH SCHOOL, the researcher's esteemed colleagues, for the love and unconditional support that enabled the researcher to take things with joy and inspiration despite the challenging demands of work.

His siblings: VIVIAN C. PORTAJE, and ELVIE C. PALIMILLO. Their love and moral support are undeniably inspiring to the researcher; His brother-in-law CHARLIE J. PALOMILLO and his nephews, CHAREL C. PALOMILLO, PAUL IVAN C. PORTAJE, BENEDICT C. PORTAJE, CHARLES C. PALOMILLO and niece, CHRISTELA C. PALOMILLO, for the significant help extended;

His parents: VICENTE P. CERDANA and ANGELA C. CERDANA with his Parent-in-law: MR. EDDIE HERMO and ERLITA HERMO. Their unceasing encouragement, love, support financially, spiritually and emotionally.

DAISY JOY H. CERDANA, the researcher's spouse. She has been his pillar from the start to the finish of all this endeavor. She is truly a God-sent to the researcher.

Above all, the researcher humbly acknowledges the ALMIGHTY GOD, who provides everything and Who sets perfectly according to His will. He is the lone source of life, strength, knowledge, and wisdom. In Him, the researcher brings back all the glory and honor.

REFERENCES

- Albarico, et. al., (2014). A Gateway to Global Competitiveness, Adequacy of Instructional Materials Used by Teachers Teaching Technology and Livelihood Education.
- Bantillo, R. B., & Ngag, J. B. J. U. (2024). CHANGING LANDSCAPE OF FILIPINO EDUCATION: TEACHERS' PERSPECTIVES ON TRADITIONAL VS. MODERNIZED APPROACHES TO TEACHING FILIPINO. *Ignatian International Journal for Multidisciplinary Research*, 2(6), 2409–2420. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12635314>
- Bhandari, P. (2021). An Introduction to Correlational Research. Retrieve from <https://www.scribbr.com/methodology/correlationalresearch>
- Choy, L. (2017). Integrating Technical Education for Workforce Development: Lessons from Singapore. *Journal of Vocational Education and Training*, 42(3), 123-140.
- Creswell, J. (2012). The Simple Random Sampling Technique. <http://repository.uin-suska.ac.id/12173/8/8.%20CHAPTER%20III.pdf>
- Department of Education. (2013). K to 12 Curriculum Guide: Social Studies. DepEd Philippines.
- Dolutan, M. N., & Ngag, J. B. J. U. (2024). LIVED EXPERIENCES OF CENTENNIAL TEACHERS IN THE EDUCATIONAL MODERNIZATION: A PHENOMENOLOGICAL ANALYSIS IN DEPED BAGUMBAYAN DISTRICT III. *Ignatian International Journal for Multidisciplinary Research*, 2(7), 22–32. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12672884>
- Kim, S. (2019). Enhancing Secondary Education through Technical Education Integration: The South Korean Experience. *International Journal of Educational Development*, 35(2), 217-235.
- Ngag, J.B. (2023). Unveiling The Literary Appreciation of Teduray Students: A Case Study Analysis of Their Works. *Boletin De Literatura Oral - Tradition Oral Literature*, 10(1), 30-3. <http://boletindeliteratuoral.com/index.php/bdlo/article/view/5>
- Ngag, J.B. (2023). Efficacy of Téduray Literature Module in Teaching English. *CEMJP*, 31(1), 404–409. <https://doi.org/10.57030/23364890.cemj.31.1.3>
- Ronquillo, K. C., & Ngag, J. B. J. U. (2024). OVERCOMING LINGUISTIC HURDLES: INVESTIGATING CHALLENGES ENCOUNTERED BY MAGUINDANAON STUDENTS IN ACHIEVING PROFICIENCY IN SPEAKING ENGLISH. *Ignatian International Journal for Multidisciplinary Research*, 2(7), 1069–1081. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13133747>